

Non thematic

The implicatures on Outdoor Media Related to the Covid-19 Appeal

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Abstract

The bloom of reports in outdoor media such as circular letter, banners, and brochures regarding the appeals in preventing Covid-19 is interesting to analyze. This study aims to describe the meaning of implicatures and the causes of implicatures found in outdoor media, namely brochures, billboards, banners, and Covid-19 circular letter in the city of Lhokseumawe, Aceh, Indonesia. The type of research used in this research is qualitative with a descriptive-qualitative approach. 30 data were taken from outdoor media from February to May 2021. The data collection technique was carried out using the listen, be free, engage (get involved), talk (Simak Bebas Libat Cakap/SBLC) technique and take notes. After the data was collected, the next step was data analysis based on the formulation of the problem, namely how the meaning of implicatures and the causes of implicatures are. The meaning of implicatures was analyzed using the equivalent method by grouping the data based on the criteria and the advanced technique used by Equalizing/Distinguishing Comparison (Hubung Banding Menyamakan/Membedakan/HBSP) technique, while the causes of implicatures were analyzed using Dell Hymes theory, namely the SPEAKING speech component. The results of this study found that the meaning of implicatures contained in external media was in the form of conventional (96.6%) and non-conventional (3.33%) implicatures with implicature meanings in form of invitations, information, and appeals. The causes of implicatures found are influenced by the background of the atmosphere, the participants, the results, the message, the tone of speech, and the form of discourse.

Keywords

Analysis, Outdoor, Media, Conventional Non-conventional, Implications.

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Introduction

Media is a means or tool for conveying messages or as a mediator between communicators and communicants in delivering messages between humans. Media is as a channel or connecting channel during the communication process (Farzipoor Saen, 2011; Wu, Zhai & Liu, 2015). In its development, the media has undergone many developments. Undeniably, this development is caused by technology and industry that are advancing rapidly (Fatehkia et al., 2020; Garaus, 2020). One of the main topics that have been reported so far in all outdoor media is about the corona virus or Covid-19 (Chatti, 2021). This virus has spread almost all over the world or more than 100 countries and claimed thousands of lives (Alfaritsi, Anggraeni & Fadhil, 2020). The rise of news in outdoor media such as circulars, banners, and brochures regarding appeals to prevent Covid-19 has made researchers interested in analyzing this news.

Pragmatics is a science that studies language and the form of speech, which is more precisely speech (Béguin, 2016; Papastephanou, 2004; Romero-Trillo, 2018). External media can be used as objects for implicature studies considering that external media has a very broad scope in society. The text contained in the outdoor media contains implicit speech; there is an implied meaning in the speech. Speeches that imply something that has this meaning are called implicatures. Implicature is part of pragmatics which has an important thing that must be observed, namely the speech context (Ningtias, Rohmadi & Suyitno, 2014). Context is an inseparable part of the text. The interpretation of speech interaction is influenced by the context of the situation and culture.

This study describes the meaning of implicatures and the causes of implicatures in outdoor media that are contained in brochures, billboards, banners, and Covid-19 circulars in Lhokseumawe City. Based on what has been said above, the urgency of this research; for writers on the media: to be wiser in involving the use of good, correct, and polite language for readers; readers: for to be the clue in understanding implicature utterances and being able to respond in good, correct, and polite language; news researcher: can provide consideration of objects that still need to be developed, especially in terms of form, meaning, and reasons of using implicatures in other concrete situations to make them more useful for language users.

1. Implicature in Pragmatics

Discourse elements that will be analyzed in this study is implicature. In order to understand what the speaker means, the interlocutor must interpret his utterances (Nadar, 2009). Implicature is one of the topics discussed in pragmatics besides diction, presuppositions, speech acts, and aspects of discourse structure. Implicature comes from the verb 'to imply' while the noun is 'implication'. This verb comes from the Latin 'plicare' which means 'to fold' so that to understand what is being folded or stored must be done by opening it. In order to understand what the speaker means, the interlocutor must always interpret his speech.

Implicature is an utterance that implies something different from what was actually said (Hermanto, 2017). The something "different" is the speaker's intention that is not stated explicitly, in other words implicatures are hidden intentions, desires, or expressions of the heart. According to Grice, implicature is divided into two, namely (a) conventional implicature, and (b) non-conventional. Conventional implicature is the meaning of an utterance that is conventionally or generally accepted by society, while non-conventional implicature is an utterance that implies something different from what it actually is.

Implicatures are not expressed literally by speakers through speech, but there are other meanings that must be assumed by speakers. Implicature is easy for speakers to understand if both know each other and have experienced the topic experienced by the speaker. Implicatures can still not be known certainly if the speaker does not know the speaker's speech with the conditions accompanying the speech, especially the context. Mostly an utterance implies something and that something is hidden behind the literal of the utterance. This happens due to implicatures (Syaikhoh, Santoso & Winarsih, 2018).

In line with Leech, (Rahardi, 2003) reveals that the relationship between speeches is not absolute in the implicature. So, in implicature the relationship between the proposition and the speech implying it does not have to be absolute. Possibly, an utterance has a variety of meaning implicatures. Based on the explanation of the definition above, it can be concluded that implicature is the meaning of utterance that is conveyed implicitly in a conversation (Cohen & Krifka, 2014). The implied meaning can be in the form of suggestions, invitations, or appeals that are not conveyed in a straightforward manner (Bar-Lev, 2021; Chien, 2008).

The study of implicatures is felt to be important and even its relation to the context will be able to explain the implicit intentions of the speaker's speech acts. The understanding of the interlocutor in the context will not be the same as each other, that it results different meanings. Based on this phenomenon, the authors examine how the meaning of implicatures and the causes of implicatures occur in external media (billboards, banners, circulars letter, and brochures) as the formulation of the problem in this study.

2. Call for Covid-19 Prevention in Outdoor Media

There has been a lot of research on implicatures and contexts, but not much has been done in outdoor media, especially those related to the Covid-19 appeal. However, there are several

studies that are in line with this, such as that conducted by Arifianti (2018) with the research title "Conventional and Non-Conventional Implicatures of Visitors' Speech in Lawang Sewu Semarang Region, Central Java" which produces conventional and unconventional speech forms. Meanwhile, Fajrin et al., (2019) about "The Situation Context and Implicatures in the 'Semarang' and 'Sirpong' Suara Merdeka Daily Columns" found that there was an implicative language used in the discourse. The form of discourse is in the form of news or opinions and comments or responses from the editors. Another implicature study that is in line with this research is the result of Sari et al., (2021) entitled "Analysis on the Meaning of Implicatures in Public Service Advertising Discourse on Social Media" with the findings that there are 3 meanings of implicature, namely appeals/invitations, prohibitions, and warnings. It can also be seen from the study of Perizga et al (2021) entitled "Implicatures in the Covid-19 Discourse on Instagram" which found that there are two types of implicatures, namely conventional implicatures and conversational implicatures. Another implicature on social media is a study by Nurrahma (2018) with the title "Implications of Net Citizens Hate Speech on Instagram Social Media (Indonesian Political Issues 2017)" which contains the conclusion that the implicatures in netizens' hate speech include implicatures in the form of anti-criticism hate speech, failure to move -on, and Islamophobia. The same thing was also done by Astuti et al (2019) with the article title "Analysis on Implicatures in Political Meme Discourse on Instagram Accounts" which resulted the conclusion that the meaning of implicatures contained in political memes were in the form of political orders, political promises, satire, political anger, etc.

Implicature analysis was also studied by Irma & Hikmah (2021) with the study title "Analysis on Conventional Implicature of Memes in Radar Tegal Newspaper" with research results in form of an explanation of conventional implicatures in Radar Tegal newspaper memes. In addition, an implicature study has also been carried out on advertisements by Fawziyyah & Santoso (2017) with the title "Conversational Implicatures in Cosmetics Advertisements on Television: Pragmatic Studies" with the findings that there are three forms of implicature, namely representative implicature, directive-representative, and expressive-representative. Another one is Yuniarti's (2016) study with the title "Conversational Implicature in Humor Conversation" which contains the conclusion that there are implicatures in humorous conversations that often occur in the form of satire, ridicule, and flattery of entertaining jokes. Furthermore, the research conducted by Ningtias et al (2014) examined "Implicature Analysis in Donny Dhiringantoro's 5 cm Novel" which contained the conclusion that there are two types of implicatures in this novel, namely conversational implicatures and conventional implicatures. Another implicature study in literary works is the study of Nurhamidah (2021) with the title "Implicature in Alfatah Nando's Short Movie Terlanjur Mencinta" with the conclusion that general conversational implicatures are identified, namely 12 implicatures in which 42% are due to violation of the maxim of etiquette, 33% are associated with maxim of relation, 17% for maxim of quantity, and 8% for maxim of quality. In addition, 4 conventional implicatures are found in the monologue. This study concludes that implicatures can be easily understood through the context of the situation.

The study of implicature is indeed interesting to study, not only on political discourse, but also on social media, electronics, and literary works. As Khairat (2018) said "Implicature in political discourse is one of interesting problems to be studied in linguistics". El khairat researched "Implicatures in Political Discourse on Indonesia lawyers Club Show" with the conclusion that implicatures have been found and used in political discourse at the Indonesia Lawyers Club by violating the principle of cooperation in declarative and negative forms, while interrogatives were not found in this broadcast.

Rahayu (2019) wrote the results of a study entitled "The Causes of Conversational Implicatures in Javanese Humor Discourse on The Thengil Rubric in Ancas Magazine" with the conclusion that the cause of the implicatures found in this study was a violation of the principles of cooperation and harmony. Meanwhile, Nugraheni (2011) wrote the results of a study entitled "Conversational Implications of Female and Male Characters in Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire Movie" by finding violations of maxims in the principle of cooperation and also the differences in the speech of male characters and women.

Previous research that has been done is different from this research. This study focuses on the types/ meanings of implicatures and the causes of implicatures found in outdoor media. The external media in this study is related to the Covid-19 appeal. Previous research analyzed implicatures in print media, social media, external media, but did not take any objects related to the Covid-19 appeal completely (Akour et al., 2021). Unlike the research results of Perizga et al (2021), this research looked at some external media. It looked at not only the meaning of implicature, but also the causes of implicatures

3. Method

The data for this research are data in the form of Indonesian texts contained in outdoor media, such as billboards, banners, circulars, and brochures related to the Covid-19 appeal in Lhokseumawe City. The data taken were 30 which were found in outdoor media from February to May 2021. The data collection technique was carried out with the technique of the listen, be free, engage (get involved), talk (Simak Bebas Libat Cakap/SBLC) technique and take notes and taking notes. In SBLC technique, the writer is not directly involved in determining the candidate data, the writer is only an observer of the speech that appears in linguistic events occurred outside of him (Sudaryanto, 2015). The note-taking technique is an advanced technique that is used when applying the listening method with advanced techniques (Mahsun, 2005). After the data is collected, the next step is data analysis based on the formulation of problem in this study.

The data that has been collected was analyzed based on conventional and non-conventional implicatures through the matching method. The matching method is a data analysis method whose determinants are outside, apart and not part of the language being studied. The matching method used is the pragmatic matching method. The pragmatic matching method is a matching method in which the determining tool is the speech partner (Sudaryanto, 2015). The matching method is carried out by grouping the data based on the criteria, and the advanced technique used is the Equating/Distinguishing Comparative Technique (Hubung Banding Menyamakan/Membedakan (HBSP)), while the causes of implicatures are described according to the results of the implicature meaning analyzed by Dell Hymes theory (Hymes, 1974) which contains 8 speech components. SPEAKING. Dell Hymes theory formulates the determinants in the context of a situation that is not much different from the previous explanation through the acronym SPEAKING. Each phoneme represents the intended determining factor. The components of SPEAKING, namely setting or scene (place and time), participants (participants of speech acts), ends (goals to be achieved by speech participants), act of sequences (form and content of something being discussed, words spoken and how relation to the topic being discussed), key (tone of voice, emotional state of the speaker), instrumentalities (the media used), norms (linguistic norms adopted by a language community) and genres (types of discourse).

4. Research Results and Discussion

Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that 96.6% of conventional implicatures and 3.33% of non-conventional implicatures from 30 sample number. From this number, it was found 5 from billboards, 18 from banners, 5 from circular letter and 1 from brochures for conventional implicatures,. For unconventional implicatures, only 1 banner was found. The following will describe in detail the results of the meaning of implicatures.

4.1. Konvensional Implicature

Conventional implicatures are implicatures that are obtained directly from the meaning of the word and not from the principle of conversation. The meanings contained in conventional implicatures are durable and generally known. So, this conventional implicature is determined by the conventional meaning of the words used. The next sub-chapter will explain the results of conventional implicatures found in billboards, banners, circulars letter, and brochures.

4.1.1 Billboards

Figure 1. Billboards inviting to Use a Mask

The billboard above is located at the Simpang Taman Riyadhah, Lhokseumawe. It is written THANK YOU FOR USING MASK HOPE THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ENDS SOON AMEN! The billboards have been interpreted in various ways by the community, for example: the government thanking the community for being aware of preventing the transmission of Covid-19 by using masks, and the government, in this case the police, was also praying that the Covid-19 pandemic will end soon. The police took the public's heart subtly by inviting the public to wear masks. It can be seen by the use of the word 'thank you'. This context is the background of the government to take people's hearts to be aware of the use of masks in daily activities. This can be analyzed by using an equalizing comparison technique that the speech in the text can be equated with the speech 'thank you for preventing the transmission of Covid-19'. The meaning of this text can be understood directly by the public therefore, this text is classified as conventional implicature.

Figure 2. Billboards inviting to respect health protocol

The text on the billboard above reads **CORONA VIRUS IS NOT MANIPULATION. WEAR A MASK, KEEP YOUR DISTANCE AND FOLLOW THE HEALTH PROTOCOL. REMEMBER COVID, REMEMBER ALLAH, WEAR MASK.** The implicatures on the billboards in front of the Islamic Center Mosque are also classified into conventional types. The meaning of this data can be interpreted in the form of orders and expectations from Aceh Government to the community to respect the health protocols. This is corroborated by the statement that the corona virus is not manipulation. So, people must believe that Covid-19 exists. The government aggressively expects people to wear masks, that a statement appears on the banner 'remember CoViD, remember Allah, remember mask'. This gives rise to a meaning that subtly asks people to remember CoViD and remember Allah because Covid-19 is God's preordination, so prevent it by wearing masks. This can be analyzed by using an equalizing comparison technique so that the speech in the text can be identical with the speech 'let's obey the health protocol to prevent Covid-19 by wearing a mask'.

Figure 3. Billboards informing Covid-19 patient

The text on the billboard above at the Simpang AURI Field in Lhokseumawe City is very interesting because it reads **SYEDARA LOEN MANDUM BEK JEUT KEU KORBAN BERIKUT JIH RUMOH SAKET CUT MEUTIA NGON KESREM KA PUNOH, PASIEN COVID TOTAL 556 DROE UREUNG LEBEH KA MEUNINGGAI DI ACEH, SYEDARA LON BEK TUWE PAKAI MASKER NGOEN TAATI PROKES.** The implicature on the

billboard above contains an implicit meaning, namely the government's hope that the public respects the health protocol. The government also announced the number of victims of Covid-19. The government subtly sarcastically touched on the number of Covid-19 victims with the words 'rumoh saket ka punoh'. This means that the community must comply with health protocols so that the number of victims does not increase because the hospital is full (Liem et al., 2021). This can be analyzed by using an equalizing comparison technique so that the speech in the text is identical with the speech 'respects the health protocol in order that the number of victims does not increase'.

4.1.2 Banner

Figure 4. Banner containing Covid-19 Prevention Information

The conventional implicature in the data found in front of the House of Representative in Lhokseumawe City implies that the government expects the public to fight the corona virus by not stopping to wear masks. This means that people must be obedient in wearing masks. The government expects the public to break the chain of corona distribution by wearing masks during the current pandemic. This can be analyzed by using the comparison-matching technique so that the speech in the text can be equated to the speech 'wear a mask to stop the spread of Covid-19'.

Figure 5. Banner containing an Invitation to have Vaccines

The implicature in the data in front of Public Health Office of Lhokseumawe City can be interpreted as an invitation to have vaccines to the community to protect themselves and their

families. In this case, the understanding is a little ambiguous because it is followed by the speech “the goodness of the here and the hereafter’. Vaccines are one solution to prevent the transmission of COVID, but it has nothing to do with goodness in the afterlife. Vaccines are useful for body health while in the world (Kotani, Tamura, & Nejima, 2021). With a healthy body, worship is maximized for the good of the hereafter. This can be analyzed by using a contrasting comparison technique so that the speech in the text can be replaced with the speech 'let's get vaccinated so that the body is healthy to do activities in this world for the best in the hereafter'.

Figure 6. Banner informing about covid-19 patient care.

The data above found in Kesrem Hospital of Lhokseumawe City contained an implicit meaning that people do not need to be afraid to go to the hospital because the hospital still follows health procedures. The Hospital in Lhokseumawe stated that there was no need to worry about going to the hospital even though there was an outbreak of the corona virus because the hospital services was in accordance with health protocols. This is because people are worried because about the issues of going to the hospital during the pandemic, making them worse. This can be analyzed by using an equalizing comparison technique so that the utterance in the text can be equated with the utterance 'going to the hospital for treatment because the service is in accordance with the Covid-19 prevention procedure'.

4.1.3 Brochure

Figure 7. Brochure Informing about Corona Virus

The data above is classified into the conventional type of implicature meaning. The meaning of this brochure can be understood in the form of hopes for school residents and the community to have knowledge about Covid-19 and its prevention. This brochure contains instructions for school member, especially in recognizing more deeply about the Covid-19 virus. This can be analyzed using the comparison-matching technique that the speech in the text can be equated with the speech 'Covid-19 is an infectious disease through coughing/sneezing droplets with symptoms such as fever, flu, shortness of breath, sore throat, and lost smell.

4.1.4 Circular Letter

Banda Aceh, 07 Mei 2021 M
25 Ramadhan 1442 H

Nomor : 551/624
Sifat : Segera
Lampiran : -
Hal : Kebijakan Kearifan Lokal terhadap Operasional Angkutan AKDP

Yang Terhormat :
1. Ketua DPD Organda Aceh;
2. Direktur Perusahaan Angkutan Antar Kota Dalam Provinsi (AKDP) Se-Aceh

di -
Tempat

1. Memperhatikan Surat Dewan Pimpinan Daerah Organda Aceh Nomor: 054/DPD-PA/V/2021 perihal Usulan Kebijakan Kearifan Lokal terhadap Operasional Angkutan AKDP, mengusulkan kepada Pemerintah Aceh melalui Dinas Perhubungan Aceh agar dapat mengeluarkan kebijakan operasional AKDP dengan sistem wilayah aglomerasi.
2. Gubernur Aceh selaku Ketua Satuan Tugas Penanganan COVID-19 di Aceh telah menerbitkan Edaran Nomor: 440/8833 Tahun 2021 tentang Pengendalian Transportasi selama Masa Idul Fitri 1442 Hijriah. Menetapkan kawasan pusat perdagangan dan distribusi Aceh sebagai kawasan pengecualian terhadap larangan pengangkutan atau pengoperasian sarana transportasi darat pada masa peniadaan mudik tanggal 6 Mei sampai dengan 17 Mei 2021, tersebar di 6 (enam) zona :
 - a. Zona Pusat (Sabang, Banda Aceh, Aceh Besar & Pidie);
 - b. Zona Utara (Pidie Jaya, Bireuen, Lhokseumawe, Aceh Utara, Aceh Tengah, & Bener Meriah);
 - c. Zona Timur (Aceh Timur, Langsa, dan Aceh Tamiang);
 - d. Zona Tenggara (Gayo Lues, Aceh Tenggara, Subulussalam, & Singkil);
 - e. Zona Selatan (Aceh Selatan, Aceh Barat Daya, & Simeulue);
 - f. Zona Barat (Aceh Barat, Nagan Raya, & Aceh Jaya).
3. Menindaklanjuti regulasi tersebut di atas, Dinas Perhubungan Aceh dengan ini mengizinkan perusahaan angkutan Antar Kota Dalam Provinsi (AKDP) untuk beroperasi dalam zona yang ditetapkan oleh Gubernur Aceh selaku Ketua Satuan Tugas Penanganan COVID-19 di Aceh pada masa peniadaan mudik.
4. Demikian disampaikan, dalam hal terjadi perubahan dan/atau diterbitkan regulasi lebih baru, maka akan disesuaikan kembali, atas perhatian dan kerja sama yang baik diucapkan terima kasih.

KEPALA DINAS PERHUBUNGAN ACEH

DINAS PERHUBUNGAN
PERHUBUNGAN NT, MT
PEMBINA UTAMA MUDA
NIP. 19631231 199703 1 014

Tembusan:
1. Gubernur Aceh (sebagai laporan);
2. Dirantas Polda Aceh;
3. Kepala Balai Pengelola Transportasi Darat Wil. I - Aceh;
4. Ketua Satgas Covid-19 Kab/Kota se-Aceh;
5. Kepala Dinas Perhubungan Kab/Kota se-Aceh;
6. Ketua DPC Organda Kab/Kota se-Aceh.

Figure 8. Circular Letter informing about inter-city within Province (AKDP) Operation

The data above is also classified as conventional implicature because its meaning can be directly understood by the reader. This data contains the meaning in the form of a local wisdom policy permit for Inter-city within province (Antar Kota Dalam Provinsi (AKDP)) operations. The transportation service and instructions from the Aceh Governor as the head of

the Covid-19 handling task force allow AKDP transportation companies to operate in accordance with local wisdom policies, meaning that Inter-City Within Provinces (AKDP) transportation can operate within a predetermined zone. This can be analyzed by using an equalizing comparison technique that the utterance in the text can be equated with the utterance 'The Department of transportation and the instructions of the Governor of Aceh as the head of the COVID-19 handling task force allow AKDP transportation to operate in accordance with the 6 zones that have been determined'.

Figure 9. Circular Letter of Lecture Information in Ramadhan Month

The data in the circular letter above contains an implicit meaning in form of information on the implementation of teaching and learning carried out online during the month of Ramadhan and during the covid pandemic. The Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic campus informed that during this pandemic and coincided with the month of Ramadhan, learning was carried out online until further notification from the campus. This action was taken as an effort to prevent Covid-19 in the campus environment (Moser, Wei & Brenner, 2021). This can be analyzed by using the comparison-matching technique that the speech in the text can be equated with the speech “regarding to the Covid-19 pandemic and coinciding with the month of Ramadhan, learning is carried out online until further notification from the campus'.

Figure 10. Circular of Information on Online Lectures

The data in the circular above is classified as conventional implicature which contains an implicit meaning, namely the policy of the IAIN Lhokseumawe campus in the implementation of online learning. The campus informed the wider community, especially the IAIN Lhokseumawe academic community (lecturers, staff, and students) that during this pandemic, learning activities were carried out online as an effort to prevent the spread of Covid-19, especially in the IAIN Lhokseumawe campus area and protect the entire IAIN Lhokseumawe academic community. This can be analyzed by using an equalizing comparison technique that the speech in the text can be equated with the speech 'regarding to the situation of covid pandemic and preventing transmission, learning activities at the IAIN Lhokseumawe campus are carried out online until further instructions are given'.

4.2 Non-Conventional Implicature

Non-conventional implicatures occur only during conversation. Therefore, the implicature is temporary or occurs during an act of conversation and something that is implied does not have a direct relationship with the spoken utterance. Non-conventional implicatures are highly dependent on the context in which the event occurs. Generally, the speech is not easily understood by the interlocutor because the meaning is implied. Non-conventional implicatures

are found in one data among the 4 media analyzed, namely on banners. Figure 1 below is a banner that is classified into Non-conventional implicatures.

Figure 11. Information banner on Covid prevention

The text on the banner above is classified as non-conventional implicature because the text is difficult to understand directly by the public. The data above has an implicit intention, namely that the government of Gampong Hagu Selatan is very strong and independent in preventing Covid-19. This can be seen on the banners posted in front of the village office and prayer room in Gampong Hagu Selatan. The government of Gampong Hagu Selatan is very aggressive in preventing covid by installing several billboards in the local area as a form of concern for the community. This can be analyzed by using a differential comparison technique that the speech in the text can be replaced with the speech that 'The Government of Gampong Hagu Selatan autonomously prevents Covid-19'.

Based on the results of the analysis of implicature types from the 30 data analyzed, the percentage of the total number of data classified into conventional and non-conventional implicatures can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. The Percentage of implicature type

No	Type of Implicature	Number	Percentage
1	Non-conventional	1	3,33
2	Conventional	29	96,6
	Total	30	99,99

Based on the results of the study, there are two types of implicatures found in outdoor media related to the Covid-19 appeal, namely conventional and non-conventional implicatures. Of the four media (banners, billboards, brochures, circulars) analyzed, the implicatures found contain many conventional implicatures. This is influenced by the context of the situation that makes people immediately understand the text on the media. Of the four media analyzed generally its have implicature meanings in the form of invitations, appeals, and information. The results of this study are different from the research of Ningtias et al (2014) because the research objects are different. This study examines outdoor media, while Ningtias et al (2014) examines novels. Similar to the research of Perizga et al (2021), the difference is in the object

of study. Perizga (2020) examines implicatures on Instagram accounts, while this study examines outdoor media.

Conventional implicatures are often found in outdoor media as an appreciation to writers in the media who can write using texts that are understood by the public in forms of invitations, appeals, information, even link them with local wisdom in order that people are interested in following or carrying out information that is contained in the media.

4.3 Causes of Implicature

Overall, the causes of implicatures in outdoor media (billboards, banners, brochures, and circulars) which are the study of this research are influenced by the context of the situation according to Dell Hymes' theory regarding the 8 components of SPEAKING. The Covid-19 pandemic situation brought up the appeals from the government or related agencies. This appeal is an emphasis and affirmation for the community in preventing the transmission of Covid-19. Appeals are in the form of obeying health protocols and invitations to have vaccination. In addition to complying with health protocols, vaccination activities are also carried out in order to control the Covid-19 pandemic. All parties must support in order that the implementation of vaccination can take place properly according to the government's target because the general target of the vaccination program is to reduce the number of transmissions and infections from the virus. The causes of implicatures found in this study are:

4.3.1. Place and Time Setting

In accordance with the context in outdoor media, the place where the speech takes place is in outdoor media, while the time/scene is during the Covid-19 pandemic. The reason for the government to include appeals and invitations in this setting is because outdoor media can cover larger audiences. These appeals from the government are generally understood by the public due to the same context and reality, namely the condition of the Covid-19 pandemic. Place and setting are factors that can influence implicatures in interpreting a text, co text, and context. The meaning of context in this case can give birth to various implicit meanings for people who respond to appeals in outdoor media.

4.3.2 Speech Participants

The speech participant is also one of the causes of the implicature of the text in the outdoor media. The existence of this outdoor media can help provide information or an invitation to the wider community. The speech participants will bring up various implicit meanings from the information obtained on the outdoor media so that the speech participants will later notify the appeals from the outdoor media to their partners.

4.3.3 Result

The implicit meaning of the text in outdoor media gives different results/ends to the reading community. The results here mean that people get a response from the meaning of the text

they see and read. By seeing the slogan, agency name, or company address listed on outdoor media, speech participants immediately understand and respond to the intent of the advertiser/billboard. Implicatures that can be interpreted can be conventional implicatures or non-conventional implicatures. In this study, the results obtained on outdoor media were dominated by conventional implicatures. This means that messages conveyed in this outdoor media are generally directly understood by the public.

4.3.4 Message

In this study, the act sequence/ message is one of the main causes of implicatures. This outdoor media is a communication or message tool that can be conveyed to the public through text or appeals. The messages contained in these outdoor media are responded differently by the readers. This depends on the reasoning power of the readers, which is essentially related to the context of the pandemic. However, this message provides a lot of public awareness of the current situation that requires keeping health and complying with health protocols.

4.3.5 Way/ Tone of Speech

The way or tone of speech (key) is the cause of implicatures because are heterogeneous in feeling or perceiving the delivery style in the text of the outdoor media. Some used a serious, familiar, pushy, or relaxed tone. This means that the language used is standard, some used careful choice of words, and relaxed language, especially when it is mixed with local languages in order to be seemed familiar to the speech participants. The speech in the banner is influenced by the cultural context, namely the culture of the Acehnese who are generally more sensitive to messages that are translated into local languages.

4.3.6 Genres/ Forms of Discourse

The form of discourse in the text affects the emergence of implicit meaning for society. People interpret forms of the text differently. Some interpret it as an invitation, an appeal, or just information. The form of discourse used in outdoor media indeed used written tools, therefore information must be clear to avoid misinterpretation from the speech participants. The existence of various forms of discourse is intended to attract the attention of the speech participants to be interested in the information contained.

Based on the results of the study, the cause of implicatures is influenced by the context of the situation according to Hymes' (1974) theory regarding the 8 components of SPEAKING. The components of SPEAKING, namely setting or scene (place and time), participants (participants of speech acts), ends (goals to be achieved by speech participants), act of sequences (form and content of something being discussed, words spoken and how relation to the topic being discussed), key (tone of voice, emotional state of the speaker), instrumentalities (the media used), norms (linguistic norms adopted by a language community) and genres (types of discourse).

The Covid-19 pandemic situation brought up appeals, invitations, or information from the government or related agencies. The causes of implicatures in this study are influenced by the time or pandemic period, therefore people interpret variously the meaning of texts in outdoor media. The public will inform the information on this media to other speech partners. The government's reason for posting this appeal to outdoor media is because outdoor media can be reached by all audiences.

The results of the outdoor media are dominated by conventional implicatures. This means that messages conveyed in this outdoor media are generally directly understood by the public. The way or tone of speech (key) is the cause of further implicatures because people are different in feeling or perceiving the delivery style in the text of the outdoor media. Some use a serious, familiar, pushy, or relaxed tone. This means that the language used is standard, the words choices are chosen carefully, and it also used relaxed language, especially when it is mixed with local languages so that it seems familiar to the speech participants (Abubakari, Assem & Amankwah, 2021). The speech in the banner is influenced by the cultural context, namely the culture of the Acehnese who are generally more sensitive to messages that are translated into local languages than the national language.

The findings of this study are different from those of Rahayu (2019) and Nugraheni (2011) because they both look at the causes of implicatures in terms of violating maxims. This study looks at the causes of implicatures based on 8 components of speech which are referred to as SPEAKING. So, the causes of implicatures are influenced by the setting of place/time, the participants of the speech, the results, the message, the tone of the speech, and the form of the discourse.

5. Conclusion

The meaning of implicature contained in the outdoor media is in the form of conventional and non-conventional implicatures. Based on the research results, the most dominant implicature is conventional implicature. This is because the context and reality are the same, namely the situation of the Covid-19 pandemic so that people can easily understand the meaning contained in the media. The percentage of types of implicatures obtained is 3.33% are non-conventional implicatures and 96.6% are conventional implicatures. The meanings of implicatures obtained are in forms of invitations, appeals, and information. The causes of implicatures found based on this research are the influence of the situation background, the speech participants, the results, the messages contained, the tone of the speech, and the form of discourse. Regarding to the tone of speech, it is influenced by the context of the cultural situation of the Acehnese, who are generally easy to understand if the banner is in local language because the local language used can be strongly understood by the people from rural communities. This is certainly different from the academic community who can quickly understand the meaning contained in the media.

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